

Quantum Bound States, Steady Stream and the Dirac Delta Function

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Classical mechanics usually employs two variables x, t to describe motion in the form of $x(t)$. Derivatives of this function yield velocity, acceleration etc. For a bound system, velocity (momentum) changes from one x to the next, but one does not necessarily need time to describe the scenario as one could use the pair of variables $p(x), x$ instead of $x(t), t$. An issue which arises is that $p(x)$ has double values as it is positive when the bound particle is moving to the right and negative when it is moving to the left. In such a case, time distinguishes between the two motions which occur at the same spatial point. From the point of view of energy, however, such a degeneracy at x is irrelevant because kinetic energy is $pp/2m$. Thus, it seems one may remove time from a bound state problem as long as one uses an energy (i.e. energy conservation) picture.

As a result, we propose using a $p(x_i), x_i$ model to describe a bound state with $p(x_i)$ (momentum at x_i) being different at each x_i . In order to calculate average of the absolute value of p at x_0 we suggest using a Dirac delta function $\delta(p-p(x_0))$ i.e. $\langle p \text{ at } x_0 \rangle$ related to $\{\text{Integral } dp \ p \ \delta(p-p(x_0))\}$. If one expands the delta function in terms of the basis $\exp(ipx)$, it seems that quantum mechanics for the bound state arises as a classical steady stream picture in terms of energy conservation, with $\exp(ipx)$ representing a steady stream picture of a particle with a constant momentum. We discuss informational probability properties of $\exp(ipx)$ which make it the basis of choice.

Time and Steady Stream

Classical mechanics usually characterizes a particle through $x(t)$ i.e. time is essential. A steady stream picture, however, which also exists in the classical world, involves x and even velocity/momentum (with direction) without necessarily requiring any sense of time. This steady stream situation may be extended if one considers a bound particle moving first to the right and then to the left as a kind of motion with space wrapping. Another way to describe this is to say that if one only considers energy conservation, it does not matter that the particle moves backwards or forwards, it has the same energy and $p(x)$ (momentum) absolute value at x . Thus even in the classical world, one may consider describing a particle without using time which is done through Newton's conservation of energy equation:

$$p(x)p(x)/2m + V(x) = E \quad ((1))$$

One may consider calculating the average value of the absolute value of p in a bound system at a point x_0 . In such a case at each x there is a corresponding $p(x)$ so it seems one may use a Dirac delta function i.e.

$$\langle \text{absolute value of } p \text{ in a bound system at } x_0 \rangle \text{ related to } \{\text{Integral } dp \ \delta(p-p(o)) \ p \} \quad ((2))$$

where $p(o)$ is the constant value of p at a certain x

$\delta(p-p(x)) = \text{constant} \int dx \exp(i x (p-p(x)))$ ((3)) where $p(x)$ is like a $p_0 = \text{constant}$ for a certain x

This seems to give rise to the term $\exp(ipx)$ which exists for all p and all x . $p(x_0)$ is determined through energy conservation (as argued above for a steady stream scenario), thus one may consider the form of weighted $a(p)\exp(ipx)$ which satisfy energy conservation:

$$\left\{ \sum \text{over } p \frac{a(p)\exp(ipx)}{p/2m} \right\} / \left\{ \sum \text{over } p a(p)\exp(ipx) \right\} + V(x) = E \quad ((4))$$

In such a scenario, $\exp(ipx)$ seems to represent a steady state description of a constant p such that an interference of these two dimensional objects creates a steady state $prms(x)$ which satisfies energy conservation. Thus there is no need for time in the bound state description. The Dirac delta function expressed in terms of the basis $\exp(ipx)$ allows one to move from specific p values at specific x points to a set of specific steady stream p values at all x . Thus a special kind of superposition of all the constant p steady stream scenarios with appropriate weights gives rise to a kind of steady stream with specific $prms(x)$ values at each x .

It should be noted, however, that this steady stream scenario loses information in the sense that one removes time and so one does not distinguish between the particle moving to the right or left. This is a loss of some physical information that is in the problem, but does not seem to affect the notion of energy conservation. Thus this picture yields a subset of the total physical information.

Special Properties of the Basis $\exp(ipx)$

$\exp(ipx)$ is a special basis which is used to expand the Dirac delta function. Other bases are also possible so why is $\exp(ipx)$ chosen? Given that the Dirac delta function is a distribution, its expansion in terms of a basis means each basis function should also be a distribution i.e. a probability type of function. $\exp(ipx)$ is a two dimensional distribution function with information about both p and x . The norm of this vector $\exp(ipx)\exp(-ipx)$, however, is a constant which loses all information about both p and x . The loss of x information shows that all x points have the same weight which represents the steady stream picture for a particle with momentum p . The loss of p information shows that unless a reaction occurs, one does not distinguish between p values either. There is a momentum flow which is unimpeded.

One may also analyze $\exp(ipx)$ in terms of information. X is an extensive quantity or conserved quantity in the sense that one may arrive at x in many different equivalent ways i.e.

$$X_1 + X_2 + X_3 = x \quad \text{or} \quad X_5 + X_6 = x \quad \text{etc} \quad ((5))$$

In terms of probability, one multiplies in an AND situation i.e. $P(x_1)P(x_2)P(x_3) = P(x_5)P(x_6) = P(x)$. This suggests a probability form of: a^{bx} . This is the identical analysis to using reaction balance to calculate the Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution for which the conserved or extensive quantity is e i.e. $e^1 + e^2 = e$.

P momentum, however, is also a conserved or extensive quantity. If one thinks of p as being proportional to impulse, one may deliver a p1 followed by a p2 followed by a p3, but these are equivalent to delivering a p5 and then a p6 or a single delivery of p:

$$P(p_1)P(p_2)P(p_3) = P(p_5)P(p_6)=P(p) \quad ((6))$$

Thus one has the double form: a^{px} . This form, however, cannot increase or decrease indefinitely leading to a periodic form $\exp(ipx)$.

Conclusion

In conclusion, although classical mechanics describes particle motion in terms of $x(t)$, there are also steady stream scenarios which do not require the notion of time. Steady stream constant momentum motion in one direction is an example and a bound state picture is another. One might argue that in a bound state, for part of the time, a particle moves to the right and then to the left etc due to turning points, but if one only considers energy, this is like a steady stream system with space wrapping because one has a specific kinetic energy at each x. A steady stream picture is thus a subset of the full physical information, but this subset seems to contain enough information to calculate energy results.

The steady stream bound picture yields a specific absolute value of $p(x)$ momentum even though the actual value of momentum may be positive or negative at different times. Thus if one adopts the steady stream classical scenario, one may consider a delta function $\delta(p-p(x))$ at each x where $p(x)$ is considered to be the absolute value of x. This delta function may be expanded in an $\exp(i x (p-p(o)))$ expansion, where $p(o)$ is the specific value at a certain x. This leads to the presence of $\exp(ipx)$ for a fixed p which may be interpreted as a steady stream type of probability for a constant p. Given that the steady stream picture exists in the conservation of energy scenario, one may propose: $\{ \text{Sum over } p \quad p^2/2m \ a(p)\exp(ipx) \} / \{ \text{Sum over } p \ a(p)\exp(ipx) \} + V(x) = E$.

One may ask: Why should one use the basis $\exp(ipx)$? We use information arguments which suggest that for a given x, which is a conserved or extensive quantity, one may arrive at it via $x_1+x_2+x_3$, or x_5+x_6 or a single jump of x. In terms of probability this implies $P(x_1)P(x_2)P(x_3)=P(x_5)P(x_6)=P(x)$ or $P(x)$ is a to the power of bx. A similar argument holds for p so one suggests a to the power px. If probability should not grow or diminish indefinitely this implies a periodic result $\exp(ipx)$. This is a very similar argument to reaction balance $e_1+e_2=e$ and $P(e_1)P(e_2)=P(e)$ used to derive the Maxwell-Boltzmann result.